

Antioxidant potential of fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare* Mill.)

S. Birjees Bukhari^{a*}, M. I. Bhangar^a and Shahid Iqbal^b

^aFree Radical Research Laboratory, National Center of Excellence in Analytical Chemistry, University of Sindh, Jamshoro-76080, Pakistan

E-mail : birjees_bukhari2k4@yahoo.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Sargodha, Sargodha-40100, Pakistan

Manuscript received 9 March 2007, revised 5 July 2007, accepted 6 July 2007

Abstract : Fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare* Mill.) is a herb with a history of medicinal, magical and culinary uses and also used as routine supporting cooking agent. The antioxidant activity of the extracts of fennel, prepared in methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane and hexane, has been investigated. The content of total phenolics for extracts was 5.48, 4.86, 0.92, 1.06 mg/g as gallic acid equivalent respectively and was determined spectrophotometrically by Folin-Ciocalteu procedure. Antioxidant activities of the extracts were evaluated by the measurement of reducing power, metal chelating activity, and scavenging capacity by DPPH (2,2'-diphenyl-1-picryl-hydrazyl) radical. Extract from fennel showed remarkable activity for each assay. Findings of this study suggest fennel to be a potent source of antioxidants. Results from different parameter were in agreement with one another.

Keywords : Fennel, total phenolics, antioxidant activity.

Phenolic compounds are commonly found in both edible and nonedible parts of the plants. Antioxidant activity of plant extracts is due to many active phytochemicals, including vitamins, flavonoids, tocopherols, terpenoids, carotenoids, coumarins¹.

In the present study, the extract of the fennel were prepared in methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane and hexane by soxhelt continuous extraction because organic solvents have different polarity and therefore have different nature to extract the compounds, an antioxidant are polar in nature and are extracted in polar solvents like methanol and ethanol. The total phenolics content were determined by Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and antioxidant properties including chelating activity by 2,2-bipyridyl competition assay, free radical scavenging by DPPH^o and reducing power.

Results and discussion

The antioxidant activity of fennel extracts was evaluated by a series of experiments by the technique of radical scavenging. The antioxidant activity may be related to phenolics content since it has been reported that these phenolics compounds can act breaking the chain reaction of lipid², inhibiting chemiluminescence reactions³ and scavenging several reactive oxygen species⁴. The total

phenolic content was extracted with methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane and hexane by following a modified Folin-Ciocalteu reagent method⁵ (Table 1). Significant difference was observed among the extracts in the range of 5.14–0.95 mg/g of fennel extract. Highest phenolics content was observed in ethanol and least in dichloromethane.

The chelating activity of fennel extracts were examined against Fe²⁺ and reported as Na₂EDTA equivalents⁶. Table 1 showed greatest chelating activity in ethanol extract and lowest in hexane. The Na₂EDTA equivalent was 451–824 µg/g of extracts for different solvents. The

Table 1. Total phenolic content and chelating activity of organic solvent extracts of fennel expressed as gallic acid equivalent and Na₂EDTA equivalent, respectively

Sample	TPC	Chelating activity
	Gallic acid eq. (mg/g of fennel)	Na ₂ EDTA eq. (µg/g of fennel)
Methanol	5.48 ± 0.03	795 ± 2.1
Ethanol	4.86 ± 0.02	824 ± 1.7
Dichloromethane	0.92 ± 0.02	502 ± 2.3
Hexane	1.06 ± 0.03	451 ± 2.5

Data are mean ($n = 3$) ± standard deviation ($n = 3$), ($P < 0.05$), TPC = total phenolic content.

scavenging activity of the extracts was determined by DPPH^o assay⁷. Each fennel extract was evaluated for radical scavenging activities against DPPH^o. The decrease in absorbance of DPPH radical caused by antioxidants of fennel extract, results in the scavenging of the radical by hydrogen donation. Kinetic studies of DPPH^o-extract reaction were carried out to estimate scavenging activity as a function of time. Scavenging activity was nearly the same at first minute of reaction and diverges with the increase in time. Maximum difference among the extract was observed at 5 min of the reaction and the remaining amount (%) of DPPH radical at 5 min after initiation of reaction as shown 32.92, 30.59, 22.39 and 27.25 for ethanol, methanol, hexane and dichloromethane, respectively. The highest percentage DPPH scavenging activity was shown by the ethanol extract while lowest in dichloromethane.

Reducing power : Determination of the reducing power which is associated with the antioxidant activity was performed by the method of Siddhuraju and Becker⁸. It is necessary to determine the reducing power of phenolics constituents to elucidate the relationship between their antioxidant effect and reducing power. The reducing power of the extracts increase with an increase in the amount of the extract (Fig. 1). The amount of the phenolics compounds was high in methanol extract of fennel. Hence

Fig. 1. Reducing power of ethanol, methanol, dichloromethane and hexane extract of fennel. All data is reported as mean \pm S.D. ($n = 3$). Statistically significant as $P < 0.01$: (◆) control BHA, (●) methanol, (▲) ethanol, (×) dichloromethane, (*) hexane.

combining these two results, we can suggest that there may be a relationship between the 'amount of total phenolics content' and 'reducing power'.

In order to compare the reducing power of these extracts with a known reducing agent, the reducing power of the extract and BHA (butylated hydroxyanisole) were measured. The reducing powers of the extract were markedly lower than that of BHA. However, among these extracts the methanol extract of fennel has the highest reducing power. The results among different parameters are strongly correlated.

Experimental

Fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare* Mill.) sample was collected from the local market of Hyderabad, Pakistan. All the chemicals used in the experiment were of reagent quality and solvents were of the highest commercial grade and used after further purification. The absorbance was measured by Perkin-Elmer Lambda 35 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. All results were conducted triplicate and results were averaged.

References

1. L. Calucci, C. Pinzino, M. Zandomenghi, A. Capocchi, S. Ghiringhelli, F. Saviozzi and L. Galleschi, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2003, **51**, 927.
2. J. Torel, J. Cillard and P. Cillard, *Phytochemistry*, 1986, **25** 383.
3. S. R. Georgetti, R. Casagrande, V. M. Di Mambro, A. E. C. S. Azzolini and M. J. V. Fonseca, *AAPS Pharm. Sci.*, 2003, **5**, 210.
4. W. Bors, W. Heller, C. Michel and M. Saran, *Method Enzymol.*, 1990, **186**, 343.
5. S. Iqbal, M. I. Bhangar and F. Ahmed, *Food Chemistry*, 2005, **93**, 265.
6. Re. Roberta, N. Pellegrini, A. Proteggente, A. Pannala, M. Yang and C. Rice-Evans, *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*, 1999, **26**, 1231.
7. I. M. Heinonen, P. J. Lehtonen and A. I. Hopia, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1998, **46**, 25.
8. P. Siddhuraju and K. Becker, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2003, **51**, 2144.